

Role of Perfectionistic Leader on Employee Creativity with Mediating Role of Psychological Distress and Moderating Role of Trait Mindfulness

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Abstract

The objective of this research is to study the link between perfectionistic leader and employee creative performance with mediating role of psychological distress and moderating role of trait mindfulness. Literature relieve that perfectionistic leader studied in different disciplined and less in the field of organization behavioral perspectives. Data collection for this study will be conducted in three time-waves, with the first wave focusing on the perfectionistic leader, in the second wave on the psychological distress and trait mindfulness, and the third time-wave focusing on creative performance. Using a positivist, and deductive research approach, questionnaires will be utilized to collect data from Pakistani Military Accounts Departments. The sample size for this study is 298. The estimation of the model was carried out with IBM SPSS as well as Structural Equation Modelling through AMOS. All of the necessary prerequisites and the hypothesized causal path were identified and significantly supported. As the gap analysis indicates that perfectionistic leaders and their impact on organizational behavioral outcomes are in high demanded area and required more research. Future directions including various sorts of perfectionistic leaders, culture, and personality qualities into the existing research paradigm. The study's limits and implications are also examined, which will be useful for HRM professionals, researchers, practitioners, and academicians in developing strategies and leaders to reduce disastrous effects and maximize favorable results in the workplace. This is the first study to look at the link between a leader who strives for perfectionism and creativity with mediating role of psychological stress and moderating role of trait mindfulness. It is most likely one of Pakistan's pioneering initiatives to explore the perfectionism in terms of public sector organizations. Thus, it would be added significant contribution in the existing body of literature.

Keywords: Perfectionistic leader, psychological distress, trait mindfulness, creative performance, cognitive appraisal theory

1. Introduction

Organizations in the late 20th century, the pursuit of perfectionism had a significant influence in the organization, which predicted different outcomes. Based on prior studies and literature, the desire to be perfect is predominant, and the number of perfectionists has been grown in last three decades. People who are perfectionistic personality strive for perfection and establish unrealistically high standards of goals, which are followed by excessively critical assessments of self-behavior. Moreover, Studies shown that perfectionistic have more negative experiences to failure than non-perfectionists (Xu et al., 2022). A small number of researches is well-known about the perfectionist leader and stress in organization. It is important to learn more about how perfectionist's leader in the workplace, they react over time is an interesting phenomenon. The existing literature highlights a research limitation on perfectionistic leader and their outcomes, as perfectionistic leader primarily studied in the fields of sports science, education, psychology, counseling, and medicine (Curran et al., 2019; Ocampo et al., 2020) and relatively ignored in work context and behavioral perspectives. Therefore, it is interesting to investigate an integrated model on perfectionistic leader within an organizational context. In the early years of the 21st century, where the world became a global village, leaders set unrealistic goals, crafting well-designed and hard or impossible activities, and fastening business matters to achieve targets. When these targets are not attainable by perfectionistic leader s/he coerce subordinates, resulted in negative perceptions within the employees. As a result, perfectionism causes creative performance through psychological distress is an interesting phenomenon. Current study also address in moderating role of trait mindfulness between perfectionistic and psychological distress, shown that when individuals are low in mindfulness undesirable waves generate in organization which strengthen employee psychological distress and when this personality style is high employee try to overcome inadequate work related things and hence increase their performance which are useful for organization as well as both for leader – subordinate dyadic relation. Drawing upon the cognitive appraisal theory of stress proposed by Lazarus and Folkman (1984) current study addressing the following research objectives 1. To find out the relationship between perfectionistic leader and creative performance with mediating role of psychological distress. 2. To testifying and knowing the moderating effect of trail mindfulness on the relationship between perfectionistic leaders and psychological distress

2. Literature Review

2.1. Perfectionistic leader and Creative Performance

Although research into the correlation between perfectionism and achievement has been conducted in a range of different disciplines, the impact of perfectionism on creative output in the workplace setting has received relatively little attention. Ability to present novel thoughts and ideas and implement them in a way that achieves the desired objectives, or the ability to do so as a result of creative performance, can be defined as the ability to transform novel

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ideas into desired objectives (Dabak, & Mulla, 2022). The capability or ability of individual to think creative and come up with positive solutions to problems is strongly related to creative performance. According to Amabile et al. (2005), creativity is defined as the production of new thoughts for transforming systems in order to meet organizational goals, and creative performance of an individual is the new and unique approach of performing an assigned work. It is essential for organization to have a workforce that is creative, as this will assist the organization to accomplish its aims and objectives in an efficient and timely manner. The causes of creative performance are eagerly sought after by academics and business professionals. One of the most crucial actions for an organization to take in order to acquire a competitive edge is creativity (Amabile et al., 1996), which is described as the development of innovative and beneficial thoughts (Zhou & Shalley, 2011). It has been hypothesized that the characteristics of leaders are a significant source of influence on employee creativity. This is on account of the fact that a leader's individual characteristics or preferences can substantially influence the motivation and behaviours of employees to pursue creative outcomes (Mainemelis et al., 2015). Moreover, perfectionism in leaders is a particularly relevant leader attribute that has not yet been explored as a predictor of employee creativity, despite the fact that it is a trait that is shared by a large number of successful leaders, including Steve Jobs (Hu et al., 2018). Following the general definitions of perfectionism (Flett & Hewitt, 2002), we conceptualize leader perfectionism as the disposition of a leader to expect subordinates to strive for excellence, flawlessness and optimal solutions, to establish excessively high standards, and to judge subordinate performance extremely critically. According to previous studies (Amabile & Pratt, 2016) has shown that creativity requires a constant pursuit of higher standards, a focus on problematic areas, and the ability to encouraging continuously to employees to accomplish set objectives, which a perfectionist leader may effectively foster. However, the all-or-nothing appraisal of performance and the excessive focus on flawlessness that are common among perfectionistic might have the potential to hinder creative thought (Kawamura et al., 2001). These debates produced to conflicting conclusions about how leader's pursuit of perfectionism effects on employee creativity and employee behavior. Recently, academics have begun to acknowledge that perfectionism can be a crucial leadership quality (Harari et al., 2018; Williams et al., 2013), however there is limited understanding about the consequences of perfectionism on creativity. Therefore, in this study, we look at how a perfectionistic leader affects the latter's creativity in organization. The development of novel and useful ideas to address work problems frequently requires individuals to pursue higher standards, learn from failures, and be persistent in seeking better solutions of problems (Amabile & Pratt, 2016). Therefore, leader perfectionism may have the potential to enhance employee creativity by motivating them to exert more effort and to persevere when facing difficulties and failures. In addition, because developing novel and useful ideas to address work problems often requires individuals to learn from failures and be persistent in seeking better solutions of (Nijstad et al., 2010). However, excessive demands and expectations from perfectionist leaders can also put stress on staff, preventing them from allocating crucial personal resources to unrestricted exploration, experimentation, and the generation of creative ideas (Smith et al., 2017). Taken together, these considerations imply that the role of perfectionistic leader on creative performance may be complex, and they emphasize the importance of investigating when and how these diverse effects may emerge.

Hypothesis 1: Perfectionistic leader has negative relationship with employee creative performance.

2.2. Perfectionistic leader and Psychological distress

In medical and some other disciplines, it has been shown that anxiety, stress, and depression are common signs of psychological distress (Eley et al., 2020). The effects of this psychological distress on an individual lead to significant health concerns such as suicidal ideation and on a professional one can eventually influence patient treatment (Dyrbye & Shanafelt, 2011). An environment characterized by intense competition, assessment and evaluation procedure, and a tough curriculum that promotes unhealthy peer competition and reinforces perfectionistic tendencies are just a few examples (Peters & King, 2012). High achievers are prone to perfectionistic. According to the findings of numerous research studies, the broad multidimensional construct of perfectionism is correlated to variety of psychological issues, both positively and negatively (Yu et al., 2016). Cognitive distortions leading to elevated levels of depression, anxiety, and stress are linked to high levels of maladaptive perfectionism (Bynum & Artino, 2018; Hu et al., 2018). Maladaptive perfectionism among medical students was found to be closely associated to neuroticism and depression in a longitudinal research conducted by Enns et al. (2001). The level of depressive symptoms was reported to be partially accounted for the amount of perfectionism scores (Bußenius & Harendza, 2019), this was discovered through an investigation into the link between perfectionism and depression symptoms in applicants to medical schools. On a continuum, perfectionism can either be a positive or negative attribute such as a strong feeling of personal accountability, having a high level of commitment, or self-destructive and maladaptive, such as the establishment of unattainable performance expectations (Peters & King, 2012). Excessive perfectionistic fears are the behavior that is damaging pattern (Blatt, 1995). A number of personality characteristics have been shown to be indicators of psychological distress as well as perfectionism (Yeshua et al., 2019; Leung et al., 2019). Yeshua et al. (2019) found that perfectionism is linked to both internalizing problems like depression, anxiety, and catastrophizing, fear of uncertainty, and elevated stress levels. These results are similar to those that were measured using the Big Five Personality Model (Costa & McCrae, 1992). According to that model, neuroticism is linked to anxiety and individuals who have un-explained wellbeing (Deary et al., 2007), which can be interpreted as a propensity toward negative affect (Smith et al., 2018). On the other personality style, such as self-motivation and cooperation are key indicators of

psychological adaptation and have been linked to psychological and physical well-being as well as high levels of resilience (Chae et al., 2019; Leung et al., 2019).

According to research conducted by O'Connor, Rasmussen, and Hawton (2010), being perfectionistic is a factor in various psychological disorders, including anxiety disorder, social and specific phobia, as a predictor of an increase in the risk of developing depression over time (Egan et al., 2011). These links can be found in either clinical and non-clinical settings. In certain cases, studies have found a significant relationship among self-oriented perfectionism and depression (Flett and Panico, 2011), although in some cases the link between perfectionism and depression have found insignificant (Besser, Flett, & Hewitt; 2010). Based on the literature reviewed above, we formulate the following hypotheses

Hypothesis 2: Perfectionistic leader has a positive impact on psychological distress.

2.3. The moderating role of Trait Mindfulness

A state of conscious awareness known as "mindfulness" is characterized by non-reactivity, non-judgment, and a concentration on the present, and without resistance or judgement noticing and embracing any feelings, ideas, or sensations that come in the present moment (Banfi & Randall (2022). Mindfulness is a state of consciousness that can be acquired by the practice of mindfulness activities. Some theories of mindfulness indicate that it is analogous to a positive personality trait in psychology and it represents a natural quality that differs among individuals (Davidson, 2010). According to the findings of several studies, mindfulness can be enhancing through the use of mindfulness-based interventions, which in turn correlates to decreased interpersonal distress and indications of increased emotional regulation (Qiu et al., 2017; Joss et al., 2020). The attention distribution for emotion regulation is directly affected by mindfulness, which also regulate emotions (Tang et al., 2020; Ding et al., 2015). Mindful people are stronger control their emotions and maintain emotional integrity, which leads to weaken negative impact and associated symptoms (Erismam & Roemer, 2010). The understanding of acceptance of negative emotions and thoughts are also facilitated by trait mindfulness, which is also inversely correlated with negative emotionality (Brown & Ryan, 2003). In the West, there is growing support that mindfulness has numerous good consequences on health and well-being, especially mental health psychology in the context of clinical management (Keng, Smoski & Robins, 2011). Mindfulness is becoming a viable tool for improving employee and organizational performance at work (Sutcliffe, Vogus, & Dane, 2016). According to meta-analyses (Bartlett et al., 2019; Slemp et al., 2019), workplace mindfulness reduces employee stress and anxiety while also enhancing wellbeing and health of employees. High positive affect or low negative affect, emotion regulation, reduced emotional reactivity, and lower emotional exhaustion have all been linked to the beneficial effects of mindfulness (Prakash & Hussain, 2015; Reb, Narayanan., Chaturvedi, & Ekkirala, 2016). Some research on mindfulness even demonstrates its detrimental effects on burnout and stress (Lomas et al., 2017). Individuals who practice mindfulness are better able to distinguish between information that is relevant and information that is irrelevant (Karelaia & Reb, 2015) which contribute to more effective decision-making (Good et al., 2016). This concept was supported by empirical research, which showed that practicing mindfulness reduced the impact of clinicians' implicit bias toward patients and enhanced clinical decision-making (Burgess, Beach, & Saha, 2017). Considering these ideas collectively, we would anticipate that when employees are in a mindful state at work, they will be confident in their ability to handle stressful situations because they are able to observe matter more concisely distinguish relevant from irrelevant information which decrease their negative state. Based on the preceding discussion and relevant literature, the following hypothesis is put forth.

Hypothesis 3: The relationship between perfectionistic leader and psychological distress is moderated by trait mindfulness, such that this positive relationship is stronger when mindfulness is low and is weaker when mindfulness behavior is high.

3. Research Methodology

For the purpose of performing data screening, and different statistical tools IBM SPSS -24 and AMOS - 24 are used. Personally, administered questionnaires with help of HR department is used for collection of data. Survey will be conducted in different time legged i.e. Time 1 data is collected from perfectionistic leaders. In time 2 data is collected for mediator and moderator, and last in time 3 data is collected for employee creative performance. Population for this study are employees of public sector organization of Pakistan, i.e., Pakistan Military Accounts Departments. Data will

be collected from top to lower level employees, comprising of Controllers, Dy.CMA, CMA, A.O, A.A.O, SA's, JA's and so on at the operational level. A convenient and non-probability sampling technique with sample size of 298 is used. In order to accomplish this study objective, questionnaires have been designed on the basis of previously developed instruments with rated from strongly disagree 1 to strongly agree 5. The perfectionistic leader (leader rated) was assessed using four items from a study conducted by Flaxman et al., 2012 using statements like *"I tend to get behind in my work because I repeat things over and over"*. Trait mindfulness (subordinate rated) adopted using 12 items developed by Feldman et al., 2007. e.g., *"I am able to accept the thoughts and feelings I have"*. Psychological distress (subordinate rated) DASS-21 by Antony et al. 1998 is used to collect the data, which consists of 7-items assessing depression (e.g., *"I felt down-hearted and blue"*), anxiety 7- items (e.g., *"I felt I was close to panic"*), and stress 7-items (e.g., *"I found it difficult to relax"*). By averaging the results from the three subscales, the total mean score was calculated; higher scores than lower scores indicate different levels of psychological distress. Creative performance (leader rated) adapted 13 items developed by George et al., (2002) for measuring the construct. An example item is: *"Suggests new ways to achieve goals or objectives"*

3.1. Demographics

The demographic analysis statistics in table 1, below give background data on the respondents used in this study. Gender analysis between males and females revealed that 68.26% were male and 31.7% were female. In age categories, majority of the sample, around 28.65%, is comprised of individuals over the age of 51, while 19.66% reflecting 41 to 50 years, 24.72% below 31 to 40 years and 24.44% fall between age 20 to 30 Years and last 2.53% are less than 20 years. The sample size included 41.29% are single, and 58.71% are married. In terms of education, 10.11% have MS/MPhil/Ph.D 12.36% completed master's degree, 51.12% Bachelors, while 26.40% of the despondences having Intermediate or below. Organizational tenure concluded that 19.38% of people are 51 and above years; whereas 28.93% fall between 16 to 20 years, 33.43% are 11 to 15 years, while 13.48% are 06 to 10 years, and 4.78% are fall less than 05 years respectively. In demographic comparison, the percentage of CMA/DCMA, AO, AAO, Auditor, and DEO level employees are 10.39%, 16.01%, 26.12%, 32.02%, and 15.45%, respectively.

Table 1: Demographics

Category		Frequency	Percent	Category		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	243	68.26	Marital	Married	209	58.71
	Female	113	31.74		Un-married	147	41.29
Age	Less than 20 Years	9	2.53	Hirlevel	CMA/DCMA	37	10.39
	20 to 30 Years	87	24.44		AO	57	16.01
	31 to 40 Years	88	24.72		AAO	93	26.12
	41 to 50 Years	70	19.66		Auditor	114	32.02
	51 and Above Years	102	28.65		DEO	55	15.45
OrgTen	Less than 5 Years	17	4.78	Qualification	Intermediate	94	26.40
	6 to 10 Years	48	13.48		Bachelors	182	51.12
	11 to 15 Years	119	33.43		Masters	44	12.36
	16 to 20 Years	103	28.93		MS/MPhil/PHD	36	10.11
	51 and Above Years	69	19.38		Total	298	100

3.2. Measurement Model

To examine the relationship between the variables, an AMOS – 24 software used for structural equation model. The fit indices for the model fell within the acceptable range, as shown in figure 1.0 and table 2.0. Model fit indices values are CMIN = 2093.205, DF= 1733.000, CMIN/DF = 1.208, CF1 = 0.979, NFI = 0.887, TLI = 0.977 represent good model fit. Similarly, RMSEA = 0.024, and PCLOSE = 1.000 demonstrated satisfactory model fit based on the recommended thresholds. The factor loadings (table 3) for each latent construct ranging from 0.754 to 0.837 and are found to be statistically significant. Similarly, the correlation between the perfectionistic leader and all other variables (mediator, moderator, and dependent) ranged from -0.466 to 0.741, which are shown in correlation table 4.

3.3. Hypothesis Testing

H1: Perfectionistic leader has negative relationship with employee creative performance.

The hypothesis predicted that perfectionistic leader would be negative relate to the creative performance. As the statistics predict that perfectionistic leader having ($\beta = -0.487$ and $p \leq 0.001$) is significant and negative effect on creative performance. The link between perfectionistic leader and employee creative performance, studies outlined in the literature were determination that two studies conducted by Goulet-Pelletier et al. (2022), found align with current study having and supportive evidence for perfectionism and creativity at work which are align with current study result, which predict negative and significantly correlates to each other. Studies examining the perfectionism and creativity link, according to Nordin-Bates (2020), have produced inconsistent results (Wigert et al. 2012; Ahmetoglu et al. 2015). Based on previous statistic current hypothesis are align with previous studies.

Table 2: Model Fit Measures

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	2093.205	--	--
DF	1733.000	--	--
CMIN/DF	1.208	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.979	>0.95	Excellent
RMSEA	0.024	<0.06	Excellent
PClose	1.000	>0.05	Excellent
NFI	0.887	>0.90	Acceptable
TLI	0.977	>0.90	Excellent

Table 3: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Predictor	Outcome	Std Beta	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)
PRFLDR	PRFLDR02	0.834				
	PRFLDR04	.811 ***	0.888	0.665	0.335	0.889
	PRFLDR03	.811 ***				
	PRFLDR01	.805 ***				
CRTVPRF07	0.789					
CRTVPRF	CRTVPRF10	.760 ***	0.938	0.604	0.474	0.939
	CRTVPRF05	.801 ***				
	CRTVPRF04	.807 ***				
	CRTVPRF03	.786 ***				
	CRTVPRF12	.766 ***				
	CRTVPRF02	.754 ***				
	CRTVPRF06	.776 ***				
	CRTVPRF09	.763 ***				
	CRTVPRF11	.765 ***				
	PSYDISA	PSYDISA09				
PSYDISA20		.763 ***				
PSYDISA04		.773 ***				
PSYDISA02		.815 ***				
PSYDISA07		.764 ***				
PSYDISD	PSYDISD16	0.778	0.85	0.586	0.541	0.85
	PSYDISD05	.760 ***				
	PSYDISD17	.774 ***				
	PSYDISD03	.750 ***				
PSYDISS	PSYDISS06	0.774	0.924	0.634	0.549	0.924
	PSYDISS13	.791 ***				
	PSYDISS12	.787 ***				
	PSYDISS08	.802 ***				
	PSYDISS01	.794 ***				
	PSYDISS11	.810 ***				
TRTMNDF	PSYDISS14	.815 ***	0.951	0.685	0.474	0.951
	TRTMNDF12	0.825				
	TRTMNDF07	.828 ***				
	TRTMNDF06	.830 ***				
	TRTMNDF10	.815 ***				
	TRTMNDF01	.826 ***				
	TRTMNDF02	.822 ***				
	TRTMNDF09	.828 ***				
	TRTMNDF04	.836 ***				
	TRTMNDF08	.837 ***				

CR = composite reliability; AVE = average variance extracted; ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05

Table 4: Correlation Analysis

	PRFLDR	CRTVPRF	PSYDISA	PSYDISD	PSYDISS	TRTMNDF
PRFLDR	0.815					
CRTVPRF	-0.466***	0.777				
PSYDISA	0.579***	-0.523***	0.788			
PSYDISD	0.507***	-0.391***	0.698***	0.766		
PSYDISS	0.557***	-0.468***	0.741***	0.736***	0.796	
TRTMNDF	0.519***	-0.688***	0.555***	0.489***	0.518***	0.827

Note: N = 298; ***p < 0.001 **p < 0.01; *p < 0.05

H2: Perfectionistic leader has a positive impact on psychological distress.

The hypothesis that perfectionistic leader has positively impact on psychological distress was run using AMOS. The result shown that perfectionistic leader ($\beta = .555$, and $p \leq 0.001$) is significant and positive effect on psychological distress, which indicate that when perfectionistic leader has high tendency to show perfectionism in the organization ultimately forwarded to employee psychological distress. Perfectionistic leader in the context of psychological distress are discussed and revealed that leader have positive impact on follower psychologically (anxiety, depression and stress). Perfectionistic leader stimuli having the potential to generate negative feelings/emotion/distress in followers. Previous study of (Wright et al., 2021) which were found positive and significant associations between depression and maladaptive perfectionism. Another, study conducted by Levine et al. (2022) shown that perfectionism was significantly associated with symptoms of depressive over time. further research by Gazica et al. (2021) also study the links between socially and self-oriented perfectionism to psychological distress and result predict that two dimensions of perfectionism (socially & self-oriented) was significantly and positively relates to psychological distress. Hence current results are aligning with above discuss literature.

H3: Psychological distress mediate the negative relationship between Perfectionistic leader and employee creative performance (i.e. Perfectionistic Leader \rightarrow Psychological distress \rightarrow creative performance).

The link between perfectionistic leader and creative performance with mediating role of psychological distress was tested and shown in figure 1 and table 5. In the first step, the direct effect of perfectionistic on employee creativity has been examined and noted negatively significant having ($\beta = -0.244$, and $p \leq 0.001$) shown that when perfectionism is high it also effects negatively with creative performance of employee. As proceed with the next step, intervening variable of psychological distress placed between perfectionistic leader and employee creative performance, tested and found that perfectionistic leader with psychological distress having ($\beta = 0.608$, and $p \leq 0.001$) positively significant, psychological distress with creative performance has ($\beta = -0.373$, and $p \leq 0.001$) negatively significant. The relationship between perfectionistic leader and creative performance with mediating role of psychological distress has been examined through sequential mediating modeling (SEM). Figure 1 and table 6 predicted that interaction term between perfectionistic leader x psychological distress x creative performance having ($\beta = -0.209$, and $p \leq 0.001$) is found negatively significant, having lower and upper value is -0.292 and -0.136, therefore indicating that current hypotheses is accepted.

Primary cognitive appraisals of challenge occur when an individual perceives external stimuli as stressful, individual may cognitively conclude the stimuli is *challenging*, *threatening*, or *harmful* (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Concluding that the individual perceive stimuli is challenging allows for the individual to frame the incoming stimuli as something to overcome. Cognitive appraisals theory of stress suggests that when an individual perceives that managers set high standards, challenging, threatening or harming which are difficult to attain, as a situation employee in organization feels psychological distress in the form of anxiety, depression and stress which untimely minimize individual performance and maximize unpleasant activities. Accordingly, the foregoing arguments and literature indicate that the current assumptions hold true in Pakistani's public sector organizations, as In public sector organization where employee job is secure, salary & allowances are pre-defined and working environment is not challenging as a matter employee are not accepted any change or challenging environments which effects negatively employee behavior, which authenticate the results and statements of previous published available literature that the perfectionistic leaders are significantly and negatively impact on employee creatively of followers via psychological distress.

H4: The relationship between perfectionistic leader and psychological distress is moderated by trait mindfulness, such that this positive relationship is stronger when mindfulness is low and is weaker when mindfulness behavior is high.

The study assessed the moderating role of trait mindfulness on the relationship between perfectionistic leader and psychological distress. Along with the moderator, an interaction term is formulated and incorporated into the model in order to investigate the specific moderating role of trait mindfulness. The results projected in table 8 shown that direct relation between perfectionistic leader and psychological distress have ($\beta = 0.3952$, t-value = 9.5984, p-value = 0.000), trait mindfulness and psychological distress having ($\beta = 0.3169$, t-value = 8.1183, p-value = 0.000) shown that trait mindfulness have significant impact on psychological distress. The results through interaction term predict negative

and significant moderating role of trait mindfulness ($\beta = -0.1094$, t -value = -2.9858 , p -value = 0.003), which supports current hypothesis.

Figure 1: Mediation effect of psychological distress

Table 5: Mediation Analysis

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Psychological Distress	<---	Perfectionistic Leader	.608	.054	10.254	***
Creative Performance	<---	Psychological Distress	-.373	.068	-5.508	***
Creative Performance	<---	Perfectionistic Leader	-.244	.061	-3.667	***

Table 6: Interaction Term

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P	Hypothesis
Perfectionistic leader X Psychological distress X creative performance	-.209	-.292	-.136	.001	H6a Accepted

Interaction effect of perfectionistic leader and trait mindfulness are found negatively significant in the predication of psychological distress. This depicts, trait mindfulness is moderating the relationship between perfectionistic leader and trait mindfulness. More ever, high trait mindfulness weakens the relationship among leader and distress. This is because mindfulness can be influencing the cognitive process of individual (Trivedi & Pattusamy, 2022). The result of this hypothesis is supported the cognitive appraisal theory, presented by Lazarus and Folkman (1984). The theory suggested that individual perceive the situation as stressful or harmful, he or she may react accordingly to the already perceived situation. In this situation mindfulness play an important role to weaken the stress situation within the organization.

Table 7: Moderation Analysis

PSYDIS	Co-eff	S.E	t-value	P-value	R-square
Constant	0.0709	0.0423	1.6765	0.0945	R-sq
PRFLDR	0.3952	0.0412	9.5984	***	0.5218
TRTMNDF	0.3169	0.039	8.1183	***	R2-chng
Int_1	-0.1094	0.0366	-2.9858	0.003	0.0121

β = unstandardized regression coefficients, S.E = standard error, *** = $p < 0.000$

Interaction plot, displayed in figure 2, further investigates the moderating influence of trait mindfulness on the relationship between perfectionistic leadership and psychological distress and indicates that mindfulness weakens the relationship between perfectionistic and distress.

Figure 2: Interaction plot of trait mindfulness

4. Conclusion

The main objective of this study is to enhance our understanding of the role of perfectionistic leader on employee creative performance. Further, the current study shed light on how perfectionistic leader causes employee creativity via psychological distress. In addition, the moderating role of trait mindfulness is also investigated. To achieve this research objective, deductive, self-administrative questionnaires and time-lagged design were used, because current integrated research model is a complicated phenomenon to understand using cognitive appraisal theory. To explore the research questions, this study utilizes quantitative data and various statistical techniques using SPSS and AMOS - 24. This study examines perfectionistic leader which are frequently characterized as exhibiting cognitive, attitudinal or behavioral characteristics. However, it is frequently believed that their exceptionally high standards contribute to more competitive and difficult settings which are harmful for organization, needs to be careful attention. The results show that perfectionistic leader is negatively and significantly related to employee creativity. Additionally, the links between perfectionistic leader and psychological distress, and creative performance are found significant and align with our research hypothesis. The result of current research also illustrates that in the relationship between leader and distress, it is moderated by trait mindfulness. This means that mindfulness weakens the relationship between perfectionistic leader and distress. Results indicate that the perfectionistic leader has the dark side or negative side too, therefore, it's crucial for organization to support employees in changing their negative perspectives about workplace (Querstret et al., 2017).

4.1. Future Research Directions

Despite incorporating all of the cognitive appraisal theory of stress and the role of the perfectionistic leader in the organization, there are still many untested theories and untapped areas for future researchers. First, there is a dearth of published research on the antecedents concerned (e.g. updated references), which warrants more investigation. Second, perfectionistic leadership is elicited different negative emotions and behaviors in the workplace; therefore, it is vitally necessary to investigate the positive aspects of perfectionistic leader with the assistance of other theoretical frameworks. Thirdly, it was explained that theories cannot be examined in isolation and must include cultural elements as boundary conditions. This can help to clarify how perfectionistic leadership affects the attitudes and behaviors of followers under different cultures. Future research may find cultural elements (e.g., individualistic, collectivistic, norms, expectations) that affect workplace perfectionism. In the work of future academics, it would be beneficial to include cultural factors as moderators in the study of the relationship between perfectionistic leader and other outcomes. Fourth, because there was not enough time to study all of the perfectionistic leadership dimensions in the current model, future scholars should test the model by adding them dimensions as available in previous literature. Fifth, the current model was only examined in public sector organizations specially in Pakistan Military Accounts Departments, which raises questions about the generalizability of the study. For a deeper understanding of the concept, the same needs to be tested in other relevant public and private sectors. Finally, studies must investigate the current hypothesis using a longitudinal research design instead of time-lagged data.

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